

Prevalence and Titre of Alpha and Beta Haemolysin Antibodies among Transfused Adults in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Haemolysin antibodies are important in blood group serology because of their involvement in blood transfusion reaction and haemolytic disease of the new born. This study was conducted to find out the prevalence of alpha (α) and beta (β) haemolysin antibodies and their titres among transfused adults in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. ABO cell and serum grouping and haemolysin detection were done using standard techniques. A total of 258 adults between the ages of 15 – 55 years were tested. One hundred and thirty one (131) adults (63 males and 68 females) who had received blood transfusion served as test subjects while 127 adults (68 males and 59 females) who had never received blood and its product before served as control. The percentage of A, B and O blood group recorded were groups A (25.3%), B (17.6%), AB (3.1%), O (57.4%). The prevalence of haemolysin antibodies were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher (68.8%) in the transfused subjects than in the control subjects. Group O subjects readily made haemolysin antibodies in the order of αα, α and α. The mean titre obtained in the transfused subjects was ¼ while that obtained in the control subjects was ½. The significantly higher haemolysin antibodies obtained in the transfused adults indicates a risk in the use of blood as therapeutic agents.

Keywords: ABO blood Group System, Haemolysin, Antibodies, Titre.

INTRODUCTION

Transfusion of blood and blood components has long been regarded as an effective therapy for the correction of various haematological disorders (1). In recent years, attention has been directed towards the safety of blood transfusion therapy. The possibility of acquiring an infectious disease specifically HIV, led the medical profession as well as the general public to a more critical evaluation of transfusion practice. As a consequence of this scrutiny, there is greater interest in all possible deleterious effects of blood transfusions.

Blood belonging to group O individuals, prior to detailed study of the complement were given to A, B and AB individuals and because of this group O donors were generally accepted as universal donors and thousands of transfusion of blood group O were given in emergencies or as a matter of convenience to patients belonging to

one of the other three major three groups. Chambers (2) demonstrated that when a sufficiently large amount of blood group O was transfused into Groups A, B or AB individuals, the recipients' red cells were haemolysed due to the presence of immune anti-A and anti-B called haemolysin. Group O individuals whose sera contain haemolysin were therefore, appropriately labelled dangerous group O donors. These haemolysin or immune antibodies occur less frequently usually in response to transfusion or pregnancies, but may also be found following injection of some toxoid and vaccine (3). Haemolysin are important in blood group serology because of its involvement in blood transfusion reactions and haemolytic disease of the new born.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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A total of 258 adults between the ages of 15 – 55 years were tested. One hundred and thirty one adults (131) (63 males and 68 females) who had received 1, 2 or 3 units of blood were used as the test subjects, while 127 (68 males and 59 females) who had never received whole blood or its components served as the controls for this study. Both the test and control subjects were persons residing within Calabar Metropolis. Informed consent was obtained from each person that participated in this study. 5mls of blood was collected by venepuncture into plain bottles for the analysis. Precautions were taken to avoid haemolysis of the samples. The blood samples were allowed to clot at room temperature for two hours, and was spun at 3,500r.p.m. to obtain sera. ABO cell and serum grouping and haemolysin detection were done using standard technique of Dacie and Lewis (4).

Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analysed for level of significance (P>0.05) using Chi-square test and student “t”-test.

RESULTS

A total of 258 adults' blood samples were analysed. Table 1 shows the distribution of A, B, AB and O blood groups in transfused and non-transfused subjects in Calabar. The distribution showed no significant difference

(P>0.05) in the test subjects and those from the general population.

Table 2 shows the prevalence of alpha (á), beta (â) and alpha-beta (á â) haemolysin antibodies in both transfused and control subjects. Significantly (P<0.05) higher level of á and â haemolysin antibodies were observed in transfused subjects when compared with control subjects.

The á, â, áâ haemolysin antibodies in relation to ABO blood groups is shown in Table 3. Group A individuals readily made haemolysin antibodies (66.6%) followed by Group O individuals and lastly group B in both transfused and non-transfused subjects. Furthermore, Group O subjects who had been transfused readily made áâ haemolysin antibody more than â or á haemolysin alone.

The titre of haemolysin antibodies in transfused and control subjects is shown on Table 4. It shows that ¼ was the highest titre among the transfused subjects while ½ was the highest titre in the control subjects.

Effect of number of unit of blood transfused and production of haemolysin antibodies is shown in Table 5. Of the 131 who had transfusion, 118 received one unit of blood while 82 persons developed haemolysin antibodies, 12 persons received two units while 7 persons developed haemolysin antibodies while one person received 3 units of blood and also had haemolysin.

Table 1:
Distribution of ABO blood groups in transfused and non-transfused (control) subjects in Calabar.

Blood group	Transfused subjects (n=131) percentages	Control subjects (n=127) percentages	Dist. in the general public in percentages Emeribe (1990).
A	25.2 n=33	22.8 n=29	23.3
B	17.6 n=23	18.9 n=24	17.6
AB	3.1 n=4	3.9 n=5	3.0
O	57.3 n=75	54.3 n=63	59.0

P>0.05

Table 2:
Prevalence of á and â haemolysin antibodies in transfused subjects and control

Haemolysin type	Transfused subjects (n=131) percentages	Control subjects (n=127) Percentages
á	18.3 n=24	4.7 n=6
â	31.3 n=41	12.6 n=16
áâ	19.1 n=25	7.8 n=10
Total	68.8 n=90	25.1 n=32

P>0.05

Table 3:
Distribution pattern of á, â and áâ haemolysin antibodies in transfused subjects and control in relation to ABO blood grouping.

Percentage Blood group	Prevalence in transfused subjects			Percentage Blood group	Prevalence in transfused subjects		
	á	â	áâ		á	â	áâ
A n=33	-	66.6 n=22	-	A n=29	-	13.8 n=4	-
B n=23	43.5 n=10	-	-	B n=24	4.2 n=1	-	-
AB n=4	-	-	-	AB n=5	-	-	-
O n=75	18.6 n=14	25.3 n=19	33.3 n=25	O n=69	7.2 n=5	17.4 n=12	14.5 n=10

P<0.05

Table 4:
The Titre of haemolysin antibodies in transfused and control subjects

Titre	1/2	1/4	?	1/16	1/32
Transfused subjects	22	45	22	6	-
Control subjects	17	11	6	-	-

Table 5:
Relationship between haemolysin status and the unit of blood transfused.

No. of Transfusion	No. with haemolysin
1 n=118	82
2 n=12	7
3 n=1	1
TOTAL = 131	90

DISCUSSION

This project was aimed at finding the prevalence of alpha and beta haemolysin antibodies and their titres among transfused adults. Previous vaccination was not considered in the course of this study because the subjects could not give account of the vaccination they had at childhood, however, none of the subjects received any vaccination in the past one year preceding the study.

The study has shown a related A, B and O blood group distribution with the previous studies in Calabar (5,6). Higher prevalence of á, â and ââ haemolysin antibodies were observed in transfused subjects as compared to the controls (Table 2). This agrees with reports of Nossol (7) who observed similar findings and attributed it to possibly induction by blood products transfused.

Blood group A subjects readily made â haemolysin antibodies than group B subjects (who produces á haemolysin) in both transfused subjects

(66.6%) and the control subjects (13.8%) (Table 3). This finding is in line with previous findings by Emeribe (5) and Kirkman (8). Emeribe (5) reported a higher percentage of â haemolysin (12.1%) over á haemolysin (5.0%) among blood donors in Calabar. The reason for this finding is attributed to higher tendency of blacks to be stimulated by B substance to produce â haemolysin than A substance to produce á haemolysin. Furthermore, group O subjects who had blood transfusion readily made ââ haemolysin (33.3%) antibodies above â (25.3%) and á (18.6%) haemolysin antibodies respectively. The implication of this finding is that group O subjects are prone to developing haemolysin antibodies in the order of ââ, â, and á.

Subjects who received blood products had a higher haemolysin titre of 1/4 while the control subjects had a titre of 1/2 (Table 4). However, 22 persons who received blood had a titre of 1/8 as against 6 persons in control subjects. Six persons among the transfused

subjects had a titre of $1/16$ whereas none was recorded by the control subjects. The implication of this finding is that blood as a therapeutic agent is a factor in developing immune antibodies which may lead to blood transfusion reaction.

The number of units of blood transfused was observed not to affect the haemolysin status of the transfused subjects (Table 5). Of the 131 subjects transfused, 90 persons had haemolysin antibodies, 82 of the 90 haemolysin positive subjects; received one unit of blood, 7 persons received 2 units whereas 1 person who was positive for haemolysin antibodies received three units of blood. The implication of this finding is that a unit of blood transfused is enough to induce the production of immune antibodies.

It is known that transfusion of blood and its components is an effective therapy for the correction of various haematological disorders but the significantly higher production of immune antibodies (α and β haemolysin) as a result of blood transfusion indicate a risk in the use of blood as a therapeutic agent. It is imperative that treatment modalities which recognize the potential risk effects of blood transfusion should be considered by the clinicians and all health care providers.

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